

DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF NEAR-ZERO CTE LAMINATES, AND APPLICATION TO SPACECRAFT

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ABSTRACT

Design, analysis, and fabrication of structures to minimize thermal loading deformation are presented in four steps. These steps are laminate optimization, laminate testing, thermo-structural finite element methods verification, and finite element based system performance predictions. Tested laminates confirm ultra-low thermal-distortion structural components are possible. Spacecraft applications demonstrate superior system performance using composites. Not discussed are effects due to preload strain conditioning, microcracking and hybridization, creep, radiation, moisture saturation, and moisture rate of diffusivity [7,29-34].

Keywords: zero coefficient of thermal expansion, temperature, laminate optimization, manufacturing sensitivity, finite element analysis, spacecraft

INTRODUCTION

Thermal stability contributes another benefit to the carbon fiber reinforced epoxy materials (CFRP) which have previously demonstrated excellent stiffness - strength - toughness, micro-cracking and environmental resistance [8,9]. As a consequence, precise and dimensionally stable composite structures with new electronics and optics are creating revolutionary telescope, measurement, and antenna applications. Existing aluminum structural designs can not provide the required structural stability without complex, active thermal / mechanism control systems (high cost and risk). However, carbon fiber composites can be tailored to provide two orders of magnitude improvement for dimensional stability over aluminum with greater inherent specific stiffness and strength.

The aim of step one is to illustrate an approach to optimize CFRP laminates for high precision, thermally stable, lightweight structures. An automated computer technique based upon laminate plate theory is presented. Following laminate selection, sensitivity and probability assessment is conducted to assure delivered performance.

For step two, coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) test results are presented for moderate and ultra-high modulus pan fiber laminates in tape, fabric, and hybrid forms. Comparisons using conventional epoxy and cyanate ester modified matrices with these fibers are completed.

In step three, to obtain confidence for prediction of fabricated structures performance using the finite element method (FE), comparisons to elasticity are performed. Cases investigated are three geometries, three laminates, and two thermal profiles. A single case is illustrated for brevity.

In step four, three thermo-structural finite element deformation analyses of actual structures illustrate the performance of advanced composites as compared to aluminum. In the first analysis, a simple generic metering structure demonstrates concepts and methods. The second analysis is a stable support structure for sensor alignment relative to the spacecraft attitude control knowledge. Finally, a complete small satellite structure, incorporating complex thermal-structural distortion behavior is shown.

1. LAMINATE OPTIMIZATION FOR ZERO CTE

1.1. Introduction

The aim of step one of this paper is to illustrate an approach to optimize CFRP laminates for high precision, thermally stable, lightweight structures. With spacecraft structures, in-service deformation is often thermally induced. Structural deformation is based upon the fact that strain, ϵ , is proportional to the change in temperature, ΔT , multiplied by the material's CTE, α ,

$$\epsilon = \alpha \Delta T \tag{1}$$

As the CTE approaches zero, the resultant structure's thermal deformation (dependent on the strain) also becomes zero, regardless of the environment (i.e. change of temperature). Hence, for a dimensionally stable structure, a laminate having a low or "near-zero" CTE is necessary. Note that for some applications, a non-zero CTE is preferred, e.g. to match metal components in a joint or provide a "system" of effectively zero CTE. The subsequent discussion is applicable to any objective CTE.

For this paper, the tested material data of the M40J/F584 are shown below.

Table 1. Material Property Data for M40J/F584

Longitudinal tensile modulus, E_x (Msi)	32.8
Transverse modulus, E_y (Msi)	1.2
Poisson's ratio, ν	0.26
Shear modulus, E_s (Msi)	0.66
Longitudinal CTE, α_1	-0.14
Transverse CTE, α_2	1.5
Volume fraction, v_f (%)	62

Personal computer software based on the EXCEL [24] spreadsheet allows sensitivity study and parametric analysis of the behavior of laminates. Laminated plate theory with micro-mechanics is programmed into "Mic-Mac / In-Plane" [1]. A companion charting tool, "Chart-quick", is used to plot variation of CTE as a function of independent variables (θ , E_{11} , E_{22} , v_f , etc.).

1.2. Fundamental Behavior Of Angle-Ply And Related Laminates

Classic text book examples are first revisited. The following four figures show the CTE in both principal directions (referred to as α_1 and α_2). Figure 1a shows the CTE of an off-axis unidirectional ply; Figure 1b shows the CTE of an angle-ply laminate. An angle-ply laminate consists of an equal number of plies in $+\theta$ and $-\theta$ directions.

From Figure 1b, it can be observed that, due to the poisson coupling effect, laminate CTE values for specific ply angles are possible which are less than that of a unidirectional material. In Figure 1b, for θ of ± 20 to ± 40 degree, the α_1 is -2 to -2.5 (versus -0.14 for α_1 of the unidirectional tape, as shown in Table 1 above).

Figure 1. Coefficient of thermal expansion as a function of θ for (a) $[\theta]_8$ s; and (b) $[\pm\theta]_4$ s.

As the number of ply angles increases, the CTE behavior becomes less intuitive. Figure 2a shows the CTE of a laminate with 50 percent 0 plies and 50 percent angle-ply; Figure 2b shows the CTE of a laminate with 25 percent 0 plies, 25 percent 90 plies and 50 percent angle-ply. Note that when $\pm\theta$ equals 45 degree, the resulting laminate is quasi-isotropic $[0,90,\pm45]$ as confirmed by α_1 equaling α_2 . Examination of the fundamental trends in Figures 1 and 2 indicates potential near-zero CTE laminates.

Figure 2 Coefficient of thermal expansion as a function of θ in the following laminates (a) $[0_4, \pm\theta_2]_s$; and (b) $[0_2, 90_2, \pm\theta_2]_s$.

1.3. Laminates Optimized for Zero CTE

A common approach to optimizing a laminate for the desired CTE (or any other macro-mechanic requirement) is to determine the ply volume fractions for a fixed set of angles (e.g. find m,n,p,q in $[0m,90n,+45p,-45q]$). An EXCEL macro automates this optimization process. A datafile contains all permutations of the $\pi/4$ laminates to be used as inputs for the In-plane analysis module. A macro program file then controls the repetitive execution of In-plane, and accumulates the resulting CTE output data for each permutation in the datafile. The calculated CTE results of these permutations are subsequently sorted in ascending CTE order.

Table 2 illustrates $\pi/4$ laminates whose longitudinal CTE (α_1) varies near-zero (from -0.103 to 0.102 $\mu\epsilon / ^\circ F$) as well as the CTE's for the maximum, minimum, unidirectional, and quasi-isotropic laminates. The laminate of ID Number 151, 5 1 1 1 (representing $[0_5,90_1,+45_1,-45_1]$), has a predicted CTE of 0.016 $\mu\epsilon / ^\circ F$ which most closely approximates zero.

Table 2. $\pi/4$ Laminate Permutations Sorted in Ascending CTE Order

LAMINATE ID NUMBER	# PLYS PER PLY ANGLE				CTE		Modulus	
	0	90	45	-45	alpha1	alpha2	E1	E2
133	4	0	2	2	-0.344	2.838	17.81	4.45
165	8	0	0	0	-0.140	15.000	32.80	1.20
49,50	1	0	3,4	4,3	-0.103	1.347	6.29	4.24
83,87	2	0	1,5	5,1	-0.099	2.958	10.04	3.82
146,149	5	0	0,3	3,0	-0.039	9.895	21.27	1.74
48,51	1	0	2,5	5,2	-0.032	1.641	6.26	4.03
151	5	1	1	1	0.016	1.874	22.34	6.98
164	7	1	0	0	0.047	3.050	28.90	5.16
137,138	4	1	1,2	2,1	0.070	1.576	18.74	7.50
159,160	6	1	0,1	1,0	0.090	2.738	25.29	5.56
131,135	4	0	0,4	4,0	0.102	9.692	17.37	1.77
97	2	2	2	2	0.521	0.521	11.87	11.87
45	0	8	0	0	15.000	-0.140	1.20	32.80

For these laminates, it is possible that the negative α_1 values approach twice that of a unidirectional ply (-0.34 versus -0.14 $\mu\epsilon / ^\circ\text{F}$), and there is an accompanying large variance of α_2 from 1.3 to 9.7 (one may be more preferable for metallic joint attachment). Further, seven unique laminates are within $\pm 0.1 \mu\epsilon / ^\circ\text{F}$ providing a good selection for further sensitivity and manufacturability selection. The 5 1 1 1 laminate has superior stiffness versus the 1 0 2 5 laminate (22.3 versus 6.3 Msi). The 1 0 2 5 laminate is unsuitable for reversible loading and 7 1 0 0 provides a poorly interspersed laminate which will micro-crack and whose material properties will change after environmental conditioning [24-27]. The 2 2 2 2 or [0₂,90₂,+45₂,-45₂] laminate has a CTE of 0.521, which agrees with the quasi-isotropic results indicated in Figure 2b.

1.4. Sensitivity Study

From the sorted list of the $\pi/4$ family, candidate laminates are selected for sensitivity study. Sensitivities to be investigated are layup orientation error, fiber volume, and longitudinal /transverse modulus variation.

From Table 2, the [0₁,+45₅,-45₂] and [0₄,90₁,+45₁,-45₂] laminates have a predicted CTE of less than 0.1 $\mu\epsilon / ^\circ\text{F}$. However, as can be seen in Figure 3 for slight fiber placement error (misalignment during fabrication) the effect on the resulting laminate CTE is significantly different. In this example, the 0 degree ply of the [0₁,+45₅,-45₂] laminate and the 90 degree ply of the [0₄,90₁,+45₁,-45₂] laminate is varied up to 10 degree from that specified. The [0₄,90₁,+45₁,-45₂] laminate is preferable due to the reduced sensitivity of CTE variance from fiber placement error.

Figure 4 compares the [0₇,90₁] and [0₅,90₁,+45₁,-45₁] laminates for the predicted CTE variation due to change of fiber volume fraction. Fiber volume will typically be controlled by manufacturing process and delivered raw materials variance. The two significantly different laminates have sensitivity approximately equivalent (0.04 $\mu\epsilon / ^\circ\text{F}$ for 0.10 vf variation).

Figure 3. α_1 CTE sensitivity to fiber misalignment for 1 ply of laminate ([0₁,+45₅,-45₂] and [0₄,90₁,+45₁,-45₂] laminate)

Figure 4. α_1 CTE sensitivity to volume fraction of [0₇,90₁] and [0₅,90₁,+45₁,-45₁].

As a closing example in Figure 5, for this laminate there is small variation in the predicted CTE (approximately -0.02 to -0.05 $\mu\epsilon / ^\circ\text{F}$) for simultaneously a large fiber misalignment (5 degree) coupled with a large fiber volume variation (0.10 vf).

This test laminate is [0₆,90₁,+45₂,-45₂] and was derived from possible ply volume fractions of the [0₄,90₁,+45₁,-45₂], [0₅,90₁,+45₁,-45₁], [0₆,90₁,-45₁] listed candidates. This laminate is selected due to fabrication benefits beyond the scope of this discussion (e.g. ± 45 degree ply supplied by fabric, negative CTE for fiber volume dilution due to a bonding, and cocured construction using noneycomb).

Figure 5. α_1 CTE sensitivity to fiber misalignment of one ply in the laminate ($vf=0.55$ and $vf=0.65$).

	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION
E11	2.0050E+07	9.8126E+05
E22	6.5793E+06	2.9674E+05
V12	4.4334E-01	1.7484E-02
G	3.4503E+06	1.5784E+05
ALPHA1	4.2059E-08	7.9641E-08
ALPHA2	1.8830E-06	1.7077E-07
ALPHA12	0.0000E+00	1.6360E-07

Table 3. Mean and Standard Deviations of Laminate Properties (Msi and $\mu\epsilon / ^\circ F$)

1.5. Probability Study

Statistical methods are effective for predicting reliability and functional performance, given random error in properties, load, or geometry [2-5]. The delivered mean and standard deviation of the near-zero laminate physical properties, shown in Table 3, are calculated using a normal distribution of the individual ply properties and their orientation by the code "VAR" [4]. This results in a $0.024 \mu\epsilon / ^\circ F$ variation with a 3 sigma (99% confidence) using conservative assumptions. The probability assessment supports the sensitivity predictions [2-6].

2. LAMINATE TEST RESULTS

For the second step, CTE test results are contrasted for Toray M40J and M60J fiber in tape, fabric, and hybrid forms. Included are near-zero CTE in the principal direction using the M40J fiber and also quasi-isotropic ($\pi/4$) orientations using the M60J fiber. Comparisons are conducted using conventional epoxy (Hexcel F584) and cyanate ester modified systems (Hexcel 1553/475 and Fiberite 954-1/954-3). [16]

In excess of 60 different CTE tests have been conducted with three independent labs. A commercial HARROP™ thermal dilatometer, and variations of laser interferometry were utilized. The HARROP dilatometer has been shown to have a systematic error of $0.03 \mu\epsilon / ^\circ F$. For the Michelson laser interferometry method, the CTE of plate, tube or honeycomb samples can be measured real time to CTE values as low as $10^{-9}/K$ [11-15]. A component's CTE can be measured in two or more directions simultaneously as the temperature is cycled between 94 K and 674 K. Recently developments using real time holographic measurements of structural components have been conducted but are not reported. A subset of the interferometry and dilatometer coupon level results are presented in Tables 4 and 5.

Table 4 compares laminate plate theory predictions to dilatometer test results. Unidirectional material properties for the M40J/F584 system is used to predict the hybrid laminates of different ply volume fractions. These varied ply volume fractions of the $\pi/4$ family provides a spectrum of CTE and stiffness values. There is good correlation for the test matrix of one sample per specimen to predicted values.

Table 5 contrasts equivalent unidirectional and $\pi/4$ laminates for the effect of matrix on a laminate's delivered CTE (M40J and M60J fiber). Generally, CTE variance is less than $0.05 \mu\epsilon / ^\circ F$ for the current generation epoxy versus cyanate ester blends. These results represent one to three tests per specimen of approximately equal volume fraction ($\pm 4\%$). Tests from independent labs are averaged when complementary, with the exception of discarded known test anomalies.

Table 4. Test Data Results (F designates a 0.008in fabric ply; T designates a 0.005in tape ply)

LAMINATE	EQUIVALENT PLY VOLUME FRACTION	FIBER VOLUME FRACTION vf (%)	TEST alpha 1 (μϵ / °F)	PREDICTED alpha 1 (μϵ / °F)
Uni Tape, [0T-9]	[0, 8]	61.0	-0.21	-0.14
Uni Fabric, [0F-8]	[0, 4/90, 4]	57.3	0.62	0.61
Quasi Tape, [0,45,90,-45] S	[0, 2/90, 2/45, 2/-45, 2]	61.9	0.56	0.52
Quasi Fabric, [0,45,90,-45] S	[0, 2/90, 2/45, 2/-45, 2]	57.8	0.60	0.52
[45 F, 0T, 0F, 0T, 45F]	[0, 14/90, 4/45, 8/-45, 8]	59.6	0.14	0.09
[45 F, 0T-2, 0F, 0T-2, 45F]	[0, 24/90, 4/45, 8/-45, 8]	59.7	-0.04	-0.04
[45 F, 0T, 45F, 0T, 45F]	[0, 10/45, 12/-45, 12]	59.2	-0.18	0.30
[45 F, 0T-2, 45F, 0T-2, 45F]	[0, 20/45, 12/-45, 12]	59.1	-0.34	0.35
[45 F, 0T-3, 45F, 0T-3, 45F]	[0, 30/45, 12/-45, 12]		-0.35	0.36

Table 5. Test Data Results: M40J and M60J in F584, F475, and 954-1 matrices

Fiber	Resin	Layup	(μϵ / °F)
M40J Tape	F584	UNI	-0.21
	F475	UNI	-0.25
	F584	π/4	0.54
	F475	π/4	0.75 (?)

Fiber	Resin	Layup	(μϵ / °F)
M60J Tape	F584	UNI	-0.52
	F475	UNI	-0.51
	954-1	UNI	-0.51
	F584	π/4	0.06
	F475	π/4	0.02
	954-1	π/4	-0.05

In Table 6, is a summary for the first order linear regression of CTE of an axial near-zero laminate using the three matrices. Accompanying in Fig 6, is the test data of three independent samples for each of the three laminates with either the 584, 475, or 954 matrix. Each matrix data regression is derived from three samples per matrix. The variation is less than 0.06 μϵ / °F due to matrix variation and typical manufacturing effects (θ, E₁₁, E₂₂, ν_f, etc.). Analysis predicts a 0.04 μϵ / °F for 0.10 ν_f variation and a deviation less than 0.05 versus this actual of 0.06 for combined effects.

Table 6 Summary Test Data Results: CTE (μϵ / °F) of M40J 'Near Zero' laminate (45F 0T2 0F 0T2 45F)t

Hexcel 584	-0.06
Fiberite 954-1	-0.10
Hexcel 475	-0.16

Figure 6. Experimental determination of the coefficient of thermal expansion for M40J fiber and three matrices.

3. ANALYTICAL VERIFICATION OF FINITE ELEMENT MODELS

In step three, an analytical verification study increases confidence in the finite element method for this class of application. FE solutions are compared to an elasticity derived numerical scheme and closed form method to determine a magnitude of error. Figures 7a, 7b, and 7c represent the simple geometries evaluated: in-plane, singly curved, doubly curved gradient. These geometries are coupled with isotropic, planar-isotropic, orthotropic, and anisotropic laminates and loaded in thermal gradient and uniform excursion. In all examples accuracy is dependent upon solution code and platform: typically these solutions have accuracies to 0.0002in using engineering double precision.

Figure 7. Analytical geometries: in-plane, singly curved, doubly curved gradient

Table 7. Isotropic deformation in inches for Case (b): a 90 degree isotropic segment with 5 inch radius, subjected to $\Delta T = 100^\circ F$

SDRC/SGI [19, 20, 22]	NEPSAP/CRAY [21,23]	ELASTICITY [17, 18]
0.0039	0.0042	0.0040

Figure 8. (a) AXAF optical bench assembly; b) Pegasus class smallsat, Astraeus

4. FINITE ELEMENT STRUCTURAL EXAMPLES

Optic, electromagnetic wave (EM), and particle collection or measurement devices often require dimensionally stable support structures. The first finite element example analytically represents a dimensionally stable metering support structure, where the concentrating element (lens) is positioned relative to a collection element (Figure 8a). Less common stable structures are triangulation systems which reference two optic devices for difference measurement, thereby determining an orientation knowledge' (i.e., star trackers). In the second example, a stable structure which references the spacecraft attitude orientation (knowledge) to a measurement sensor is found on an environmental monitoring experiment supported by a earth pointing (Nadir) platform. Other applications require the entire spacecraft bus structure to be stable, as will be discussed in the closing example (Figure 8b).

Figure 9a illustrates a medium size (20in X 20in X 40in), three-dimensional rectangular frame. The composite material analysis evaluates a cocured assembly of low CTE ($0.05 \mu\epsilon / ^\circ\text{F}$) and high stiffness (20 Msi) laminate. The alignment of the forward sensor relative to the spacecraft's knowledge, after in-service thermal deformation, is compared for aluminum versus CFRP. This alignment is represented by the upper and lower planes of the rectangular frame. Analytically represented is the deformation from a reference strain-free assembly of 70 °F to the 100 °F gradient (Figures 9b and 9c). Actual orbit thermal exposure (and deformation) is time dependent and loading profiles are calculated for incremental orbit locations. These load cases are applied to the finite element model individually for distortion prediction versus time. For this load profile, the planar alignment of knowledge to sensor is 0.1107 degree for the composite material system and 0.0010 for the aluminum system (Table 8).

Figure 9. Three-dimensional frame: (a) FE geometry; (b) thermal gradient load; (c) deformations.

Table 8. FE predicted maximum Z-axis deformation and angular rotation

	+Z	-Z	angle change
Aluminum	-0.0275	+0.011136	0.1107
CFRP	-0.0002275	+0.000114	0.0010

The second FE analysis is of a geometrically complex, medium size (40 inch X 20 inch) structure supporting a forward sensor system to the spacecraft attitude control (knowledge). The CFRP support incorporates tailored laminates of M40J and M60J fiber in a cyanate ester blend matrix. This structure has minimum stiffness requirement in addition to the desired dimensional stability. A frequency analysis, depicting a 25Hz first mode, verifies the stiffness of the sensor system support (Figure 10). A single thermal load gradient case is illustrated with the respective deformation, Figures 10a and 10b. The thermal profile, due to solar exposure, is a +X gradient of 0 to 100 °F. The deformations are due to a thermal loading of this gradient relative from the reference strain-free assembly of 70 °F. The composite material structure has a predicted deformation misalignment of 0.0003 degree versus 0.056 for a geometrically equivalent aluminum system. The reduced misalignment due to the use of CFRP results in improved spacecraft system performance.

Figure 10. Support structure: (a) frequency analysis; (b) thermal gradient load; (c) deformation

Table 9. Angular Misalignment of Support Structure as a Function of Laminate Properties

CTE	0.15	0.40	10.0
E 11 (Msi)	18	18	10
Misalignment (Degrees)	0.0003	0.0017	0.056

The closing analysis is of a Pegasus-class smallsat named Astraeus (Figure 8b). The satellite primary structure (equipment section) is a CFRP, minimum part count, dimensionally stable, and low cost construction incorporating the optimizations and materials as previously discussed. The complete structure assembly is 69lb and supports 500lb of payload to low earth orbit (LEO) through a 10g launch environment. Stiffness requires a minimum global frequency of 35Hz. Core section modules incorporate provision for electronics mounting. Low CTE, high thermal conductive, iso-planar, P120 carbon fiber / boron nitride enhanced epoxy radiators are utilized at the ± Z panels. These laminates incorporated into the integral longeron reinforcement have greater than 20Msi stiffness, CTE of less than ± 0.05 µε / °F, and have been tested to 10,000lb compression. The stable structure philosophy integrates 'near-zero' axial longerons with 'low CTE' iso-planar platforms into the structure, as schematically shown in Figure 11a.

The thermal temperature profile is an actual on orbit, transient loading due to internal equipment energy dissipation and solar flux, Figure 11b. The solution is derived from a Lockheed proprietary analysis system. The deformation is illustrated without discussion, Figure 11c. Spacecraft knowledge is referenced internally to the structure, while the sensor platform is located on the +Z reference plane (the angular misalignment of this reference to the platform must be minimized). Incorporation of 'tailored' composites results in significant dimensional stability benefit (in addition to reduced weight from the higher specific stiffness and strength).

Figure 11. (a) Stability Schematic; (b) Thermal Gradient Load; (c) Deformation

CONCLUSIONS

Laminate optimization, material testing, and full structure analyses shows that superior spacecraft structures are possible with CFRP materials. Simple, personal computer software automates the optimization, sensitivity assessment, and statistical variation prediction to assist in laminate selection. Sensitivity examples illustrate that properly selected laminates have an insensitive behavior to manufacturing and material variation. Tested laminates of M40J and M60J confirm ultra-low thermal-distortion structural components are possible.

Test data correlates well with the analytical predictions, thereby providing confidence to develop full scale stable structures. A tailored M40J laminate demonstrates a CTE of less than ± 0.05 with an accompanying stiffness greater than 20 Msi and high specific strength. Isoplanar M60J laminates have also demonstrated less than ± 0.05 with stiffness over 15 Msi.

Analytical verification of the finite element method, by elasticity, validates this numerical method for predicting complex full structure performance. Concluding FE analyses of existing and developmental spacecraft applications demonstrate the superior structural performance of composite materials (high specific stiffness and exceptional thermal stability).

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